

Viscosities and Partial Molar Volumes of Benzyl Triethylammonium Chloride in Ethanol-Water Mixtures at 298 K^ψ

U. R. KAPADI*^a, S. K. CHAVAN^a and P. P. HANKARE^b

^aChemistry Department, Shivaji University, Centre for Post-Graduate Studies, Solapur-413 001

^bChemistry Department, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004

Manuscript received 9 February 1994 revised 21 December 1994, accepted 6 July 1995

Measurement of viscosities and partial molar volumes in solutions provides an excellent method for obtaining data on solute-solute and solute-solvent interaction¹⁻⁴. The majority of viscosity and density data reported so far are for simple inorganic electrolytes in single solvents but these in mixed solvents are scanty. This lead us to undertake the study of ion-ion and ion-solvent interaction of benzyl triethylammonium chloride in mixed solvents.

Results and Discussion

The relative viscosities of the electrolyte at various composition of ethanol-water mixtures have been analysed by Jones-Dole equation⁴,

$$[(\eta/\eta_0)-1]/\sqrt{C} = A + B\sqrt{C} \quad (1)$$

where, η and η_0 are the viscosities of solution and solvent respectively, and C is the concentration of solute. The positive value of A (Falkenhagen⁵ coefficient) indicates the existence of strong ion-ion interaction which may presumably be due to unusual cation-cation and cation-anion interactions. The positive value of B , the Jones-Dole coefficient⁴ related to ion-solvent interactions, indicates that these interactions are strong enough and the extent of interaction is unaffected by the amount of ethanol. The values are given in Table 1.

The viscosity data has also been analysed on the basis of transition state treatment⁶ of relative viscosity of electrolytic solution. The B -coefficient in terms of this

$$B = \frac{\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0}{1000} + \frac{\bar{V}_1^0}{1000} \left(\frac{\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}}{RT} \right) \quad (2)$$

where, $\bar{V}_1^0$ and $\bar{V}_2^0$ are the partial molar volumes of the pure solvent and the solvent respectively, $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ and $\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$, the contributions per mole of solute to the total free energy of activation for viscous flow of the solution and solvent respectively, and the latter quantity is given by equation (3),

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger} = RT \ln \left(\frac{\eta_1 \bar{V}_1^0}{Nh} \right) \quad (3)$$

where, h is the Planck constant and N the Avogadro number. The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ are presented in Table 1. It is evident from these values that $\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$ is practically constant at all solvent compositions. This implies that B -coefficient is dependent mainly on $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ and $(\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)$ term. The $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ values are positive and larger than that of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$, suggest that the formation of the transition state is less favourable. The apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v) were calculated from the density data using equation (4),

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000(d_1-d)}{C d_1} + \frac{M_2}{d_1} \quad (4)$$

where C is the molarity, d_1 and d are the densities of solvent and the solution respectively, and M_2 is the molecular weight of the electrolyte. These values varied linearly with the square-root of the concentration in conformity with the Masson's equation⁷,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v^* \sqrt{C} \quad (5)$$

where, ϕ_v^0 is the apparent molar volume at infinite dilution and S_v^* the experimental slope. The values of ϕ_v^0 and S_v^* are listed in Table 1. The ϕ_v^0 values were found to be large and positive indicating the presence of strong solute-solvent interaction. The positive and large values of S_v^* indicate the presence of strong ion-ion interactions confirming the conclusion drawn on the basis of Jones-Dole equation.

Experimental

Benzyl triethylammonium chloride was synthesised using quaternarisation reaction. Benzyl chloride and triethyl amine (both A.R., SD's) were refluxed in equimolar

TABLE 1—VALUES OF DIFFERENT PARAMETERS IN ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

Ethanol % (by wt.)	A $\left(\frac{1000 \text{ ml}}{\text{mol}}\right)^{3/2}$	B $\frac{1000 \text{ ml}}{\text{mol}}$	ϕ_v^0	S_v^*	$\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$	$\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$
				$31.62 \text{ mol}^{3/2}$ mol ^{1/2}		
10	0.010	0.419	163.4	148.6	8.23	14.41
20	0.019	0.213	171.8	158.8	8.41	15.18
30	0.045	0.203	179.3	159.6	8.56	16.46
40	0.025	0.124	181.5	163.5	8.64	18.33
50	0.034	0.376	279.0	200.1	8.69	17.38
60	0.018	0.250	143.5	125.1	8.70	15.67
70	0.012	0.268	204.8	140.0	8.69	17.56
80	0.032	0.147	192.2	180.3	8.66	10.10
90	0.014	0.207	172.6	104.7	8.59	12.82

A and B least-square fit parameters; ϕ_v^0 and S_v^* computed parameters of eqn. (5).

*Present Address : School of Chemical Sciences, North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon-425 001.

^ψPresented at 30th Annual Convention of Chemists, Calcutta

NOTE

quantities for 3 h and the product was crystallised. The purity of the product was checked by tlc. Ethanol was purified by reported procedure⁸. Ethanol-water mixtures of varying compositions as well as solutions of the electrolytes were made by weight within an accuracy 0.1 mg. Density was determined using a pycnometer of about 7.5 ml volume with 10 cm long neck. Viscosity was measured using a Cannon-Ubbelohde viscometer. A high precision thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) was used throughout the work. The details of the experimental procedure have been reported elsewhere².

References

1. R. GOPAL and P. SING, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 388.
2. N. ISLAM, M. R. ISLAM and R. AHAMD, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, **17**, 285.
3. D. EAGLAND and F. POLLING, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, **76**, 1902.
4. G. JONES and M. DOLE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2950.
5. H. FALKENHAGEN and E. L. VERNAN, *Z. Phys.*, 1932, **33**, 140.
6. D. FEAKINS, J. D. FREEMANTLE and K. G. LAWRENCE, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1974, **70**, 795.
7. D. O. MASSON, *Phil. Mag.*, 1929, **8**, 218.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry". Longmans, London.